

ISic3336

I.Sicily inscription 3336

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Helorus

Place of origin (modern)

Eloro

Provenance

contr. S. Curraiuolo (during autostrada works), 5km from Eloro

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Noto, Museo Civico di
Noto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491422

EDCS 70900818

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2007.0675

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 57.0871

Vinci, M. 2007. Un nuovo epitaffio in greco della Sicilia di età alto-imperiale e il formulario con gli epiteti XPHSTOS KAI AMEMPTOS. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik*. 162: 188-192.

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3336. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388420>